

Some Novel Coordination Complexes*

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I am extremely thankful to the Council of the Indian Chemical Society for electing me to deliver Acharya P. C. Ray Memorial Lecture (1991). This is an honour which any Indian Chemist feels proud of. More so with me, since I started my teaching and research in 1948 at Ravenshaw College, Cuttack, the premier educational institution in Orissa during those days. Prof. Priyadarajan Ray, the illustrious student of that famous Guru Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray, and Prof. Pulin Bihari Sarkar were coming to Cuttack frequently and were the sources of inspiration for teachers of Inorganic Chemistry at Ravenshaw College. When I went to the University college, London in 1957 to work with Prof. Sir Ronald S. Nyholm, I was hearing from Sir Ronald the name of only one Inorganic Chemist from this country and that was Prof. P. C. Ray. So, I feel very much honoured to be elected for an award instituted to cherish the memory of that great founder Inorganic Chemist in India - Acharya P. C. Ray.

There is yet another reason to feel happy. My field of research is also coordination complexes in which Prof. P. C. Ray and his research school were pioneers in this country. It is satisfying to note that I could also make a small contribution to this fascinating field of coordination chemistry.

From the days of Alfred Werner, this branch of chemistry has undergone lots of changes with greater understanding of the nature of the chemical bond in a coordination complex. The coordination number of the central metal ion is

no longer dependent upon the size of the ligand and the space available as was earlier thought of. In the metal-ligand bond, it was considered that ligand donated electrons and metal ion accepts them. With the greater understanding of the nature of the electron and after the enunciation of Pauling's electroneutrality principle, it was realised that the metal ion is not only an electron acceptor but also an electron donor. Similarly, the ligand is also a π -acceptor besides being a σ -donor. Hence the donor-acceptor characteristics of both the metal and ligand are to be clearly understood and evaluated before formulating a picture for the coordination complex. One can play with these donor-acceptor characteristics by suitably changing the environment. A ligand donor atom can be made a richer or a poorer donor by introducing electron-repelling or electron-attracting substituents in the α -position effecting the donor electron cloud. A quantitative estimate of the ligand field parameters can be obtained spectroscopically. Having a knowledge of the ligand field strengths of different donor atoms, tailor-made compounds can be made by a judicious selection of the ligand and the metal ion. Thus, less basic ligands favour higher coordination number and more basic ligands favour lower coordination number and more basic ligands stabilise lower coordination number. Similarly with a higher valent metal ion greater coordination numbers can be obtained. For explaining the stability of zero-valent metal carbonyls and other lower valent metal complexes, the back-bonding hypothesis, whereby the improbable accumulation of negative charge on the metal ion can be

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drained out and fed back to the vacant *d*-orbitals of the donor atom has been invoked. This π -bonding mechanism superimposed on the original ligand to metal *s*-bond has gained wide acceptance in course of time. Slightly higher bond order was also confirmed by infrared spectral data and also by bond shortening in bond length measurements.

So, it was very clear that by selecting suitable metal ions and ligands and carrying out reactions in a suitable single or mixed solvent medium having optimum polarity, one can dictate the formation of a desired complex compound. Theoretically one can plan out the materials and suitable preparative techniques. When once the complex compound is isolated in a *pure condition* (this is very important), its complete characterisation offers some difficulties. One should be able to obtain convincing information regarding (i) valency of the metal ion, (ii) exact coordination number and (iii) preferred stereochemistry. The difficulties and uncertainties in characterisation are as follows. (a) Sometimes all the potential bonding sites of the ligand may not be utilised thereby decreasing the expected coordination number. (b) Dimerisation or polymerisation can increase the apparent coordination number. (c) Coordination of water molecules or presence of unbonded and loosely held ligand molecules can also bring some uncertainty. The preferred stereochemistry is also subjected to many ambiguities and uncertainties. A large number of physicochemical measurements including magnetic susceptibility, infrared and electronic spectral measurements are to be made to draw fairly safe conclusions. When once a new complex compound is characterised it becomes a material for a host of investigations. Its utility or otherwise in medicine, industry, agriculture and many other fields can be explored and accepted or rejected depending on its usefulness. The crystallographers can have a busy time with it finding out bond length and bond angle data to give a definite geometry to the molecule.

Every metal has a stable valency and some unstable valency states. Thus trivalent iron is the stablest, divalent fairly stable but zero-valent, univalent and quadrivalent are usually unstable. Similarly most of the metal ions prefer coordination numbers 4 or 6, whereas coordination numbers 3, 5, 7 and 8 are less common. It was therefore felt to keep the above outlined guiding principles in mind and attempt preparing coordination complexes with unusual valency states and less common coordination numbers. Then, they will be novel coordination complexes for which there will not be many examples in the earlier literature.

In 1962, I left Cuttack and joined Regional Engineering College, Rourkela, where a systematic and sustained work was carried out by me and a large number of my collaborators with a view to prepare some novel coordination complexes. We did not complain about the facilities we did not have, but made the best use of what little we had. A technical institution offers many more infrastructural facilities for pure research even though there are inherent restraints.

TABLE 1—METAL IONS WITH ISOELECTRONIC SEQUENCE FROM $3d^0$ TO $3d^{10}$

d^0	Ti ^{IV}	V ^V							
d^1	Ti ^{III}	V ^{IV}							
d^2	Ti ^{II}	V ^{III}	Cr ^{IV}						
d^3	<u>Ti^I</u>	V ^{II}	<u>Cr^{III}</u>	<u>Mn^{IV}</u>					
d^4	Ti ⁰	V ^I	Cr ^{II}	<u>Mn^{III}</u>	Fe ^{IV}				
d^5	Ti ⁻	V ⁰	Cr ^I	<u>Mn^{II}</u>	<u>Fe^{III}</u>	Co ^{IV}			
d^6		V ⁻	Cr ⁰	<u>Mn^I</u>	<u>Fe^{II}</u>	Co ^{III}	Ni ^{IV}		
d^7			Cr ⁻	<u>Mn⁰</u>	<u>Fe^I</u>	<u>Co^{II}</u>	<u>Ni^{III}</u>		
d^8				<u>Mn⁻</u>	<u>Fe⁰</u>	Co ^I	<u>Ni^{II}</u>	<u>Cu^{III}</u>	
d^9				Mn ²⁻	<u>Fe⁻</u>	Co ⁰	Ni ^I	<u>Cu^{II}</u>	
								(Ag ^{II})	
d^{10}				Mn ³⁻	Fe ²⁻	Co ⁻	Ni ⁰	<u>Cu^I</u>	<u>Zn^{II}</u>
								(Ag ^I)	(Cd ^{II})

Double-underline valency states not reported till now. All others are established.

Single-underlined valency states studied by Ranana Rao and coworkers.

Coordination numbers 3, 5, 7 and 8 reported by Ramana Rao and coworkers.

TABLE 2—COMPLEXES OF METALS OF THE FIRST TRANSITION SERIES ($3d^0$ TO $3d^{10}$)

Non-bonding <i>d</i> -shell	Metal ion	Coordination number	Examples
d^0, d^1, d^2	—	—	Not yet studied
d^3	Cr ^{III}	6	[Cr(bz bz/bz ac)(<i>o</i> -phen/bipy)(NCS) ₂]; (Et ₄ N)[CrCl ₃ .Br.IQ ₂]; [Cr(Stsc)(pyca)H ₂ O]
	Mn ^{IV}	6	[Mn(dtc) ₂ X ₂] (dtc = et ₂ dtc, pip.dtc, morp.dtc; X = Cl, Br)
d^4	Mn ^{III}	5	(<i>n</i> -Cetylpy.H) ₂ (MnCl ₅); [Mn(dtc) ₂ Cl]
		6	Mn(β-dik) ₂ ox; Mn(β-dik)(ox) ₂ Mn(tsc) ₂ (pyca/et ₂ dtc/acac)
d^5	Mn ^{II}	4	(R ₄ N) ₂ (MnCl ₂ Br ₂); (R ₄ N)(MnCl ₂ .Br.L); (R ₄ N)(MnX ₃ .L)
		5	(LH) ₂ (MnL.X ₂ .Y ₂) (L = subst.py, IQ; X, Y = Cl, Br)
		6	Mn(acac) ₂ L ₂ ; (MnIz ₆)(ClO ₄) ₂ ; [Mn(CO) ₂ Diars.X ₂]
		8	[Mntu ₄ .X ₂ .L ₂] (L = γ-pic, 4-vpy) MnL ₆ (NO ₃) ₂ ; (<i>n</i> -cepy) ₂ [MnCl ₄ .L ₄] (L = γ-pic, β-pic, IQ)
	Fe ^{III}	5	Fe(acac) ₂ Cl]
		6	Fe(dtc) ₂ ox; Fe(β-dik) ₂ ox; Fe(β-dik)(ox) ₂
d^6	Mn ^I	6	[Mn(CO) ₃ Diars.I]
	Fe ^{II}	4	(R ₄ N) ₂ [FeCl ₄]
		5	
		6	[Fe(CO) ₂ Diars.l ₂]
d^7	Fe ^I	5	[Fe(CO) ₂ Diars.I]; [Fe(dtc) ₂ NO]
	Co ^{II}	4	(R ₄ N)(CoX ₃ L); [(LH) ₂ (CoX ₂ Y ₂); [Co(SeU) ₄](ClO ₄) ₂
		5	[Co.tu ₃ .Cl ₂ /Br ₂]; [Co(bz bz)(Py) ₂ Cl]
		6	CoL ₄ X ₂ ; Co(β-dik) ₂ L ₂
		8	[Co(ABT) ₂ (SCN) ₂ L ₄] (L=iq, r-pic, β-pic)
	Ni ^{III}	5	[Ni(ox) ₂ X]
		6	[Ni(pyca) ₂ (acac)]
d^8	Fe ⁰	5	Fe(CO) ₃ Diars; Fe(CO)(Diars) ₂ .
	Ni ^{II}	4	(LH)(NiX ₃ L); (LH)(NiX ₂ .Y.L); [Ni(dtc)(NO) ₂]
		5	[Ni(dtc) ₂ L] (L = γ-pic, 4-vpy)
		6	[Ni(β-dik) ₂ L ₂]; [NiL ₆](ClO ₄) ₂
d^9	Cu ^{III}	4	[Cu(acac)Cl ₂]
	Cu ^{II}	4	(LH) ₂ (CuX ₄ .X ₂ Y ₂), [Cu.dtc.(NO) ₂]
		5	Cu(bz ac) ₂ L; Cu(dtc) ₂ pyNO; [Cu(bz bz)L.X] (L = bipy, <i>o</i> -phen, X = NO ₃ , ClO ₄); [CuL ₂ .SeCN]NO ₃ (L = dien, pn)
		6	CuL ₄ (NO ₃) ₂ ; CuL ₃ .I ₂ .H ₂ O; Cu(dtc) ₂ .L ₂
d^{10}	Ag ^{II}	6	[Ag(Pyca) ₂ L ₂] (L = Q, IQ, subst.Q)
	Ag ^I	2	(AgL ₂)ClO ₄ ; [Ag.L.CNS]
		3	(AgL ₂ .NO ₃) (L = Q, iq, 4-vpy) (AgL ₂ .X) (L = bzt, 2-ambzt; X = SCN ⁻ , NCO ⁻)
		4	[AgL ₃ .NO ₃]; [Ag(φ ₃ As) ₄]X (X = NO ₃ , ClO ₄) [AgL ₃ .X] (L = φ ₃ P, φ ₃ As, X = SCN ⁻ , NCO ⁻)

Zn ^{II}	4	ZnL ₂ X ₂ ; R ₄ N(ZnX ₃ .L); (LH) ₂ (ZnX ₄ , X ₂ Y ₂)
	5	Zn(β-dik) ₂ L; (Zntu ₂ .X ₂ .L); R ₄ N(ZnX ₃ .L ₂) Zn(dtc) ₂ L; [Zn(bzt) ₃ X ₂ .] (X = NCO ⁻ , N ₃); [Zn.tu.Br ₂ .L ₂] (L = Q, meq)
	6	Zntu ₂ X ₂ L ₂ ; Zntu ₄ (CNS) ₂ ; (LH)(ZnX ₃ L ₃)
Cd ^{II}	4	M(CdX ₃); M(CdX ₃ L); (CdX ₂ L ₂)
	5	Cd(β-dik) ₂ L; Cd(dtc) ₂ L; Et ₄ N[CdI ₃] [Cd(pyNO)(Q/IQ) ₂ I ₂]
	6	Cd(β-dik) ₂ L ₂
	7	[Cd(pip.dtc) ₂ IQ ₃]

Our attention was mainly confined to first transition series, and Table 1 gives metal ions with isoelectronic sequence from $3d^0$ to $3d^{10}$. The idea was to see every metal ion to exhibit as many valency states as possible and as many coordination numbers as possible by providing suitable ligand environment round the metal ion. The concept of providing hetero ligand donor atoms with different basicities to optimise conditions favourable for the formation of a desired compound was tried by us extensively in the form of *mixed ligand complexes*. Metal ions with isoelectronic configuration are expected to behave alike. Mn⁰, Fe⁴, Co⁺² and Ni³⁺ have a $3d^7$ configuration and all of them form pentacoordinated complexes. Mn⁻, Fe⁰, Co⁺ and Ni²⁺ have a $3d^8$ configuration and surprisingly they also form pentacoordinated complexes. The valency states underlined in Table 1 have been studied

by Ramana Rao and coworkers and less common coordination numbers 3, 5, 7 and 8 have been established in some cases. In Table 2 are listed complexes of metals of the first transition series prepared by Ramana Rao and his coworkers. Fellow chemists working in the field of coordination chemistry during 1962-1986 might be aware of all these complexes reported in several papers published in different research journals. Hence I need not dwell much on them and leave it to their recapitulation.

I am sure that this humble contribution of myself and my coworkers (whose names I do not mention here) is a fitting tribute to the memory of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray-the pioneer in this particular field of coordination chemistry in our country.